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Sources: (1) Foley, William: The Papuan Languages of New Guinea
Cambridge Language Surveys, 1986

(2) Foley, William: The Yimas Language of New Guinea
Stanford University Press, 1991

All examples are taken from (2), unless where exceptions noted.

The Notion of word and boundaries

- phonological criteria:
 - o final nasal plus stop cluster simplification rule only applies at the ends of words
 - o initial semivowel formation only applies at the beginning of words
 - o most of the other rules, but not palatalization occur internally
 - o stress rule: supply to every word unit at least a primary stress and possibly one or more secondary stress
- morphosyntactic criteria:
 - o morphological patterns of nouns:
 - fixed order: noun + number + case (+ internal morpheme boundary)
 - no insertion of an element possible
 - ex.: [áwku^hm] /#awklmp#/ phonological boundaries
/awklmp + l + nan/ 'wrist + DL + OBL' > [áwku^hmb^ht̃an] 'on the two wrists'

here grammatical criteria coincide with phonological criteria
 - o adjectives: inflected for class, number of their modified noun
 - ordering is rigid, nothing may be inserted
 - again coincidence between phonological and grammatical criteria
 - o coincidence vanishes in verbs:
 - negation – good diagnostic of words, for it affects both the first morpheme of a word and the last: prefix ta- occupies the first prefixal slot, usurps the normal occupier of this slot and shifting this to the final suffixal slot
 - ex.: tampaym p -ka -apca -t
hook.VII.SG VII.SG.O-1SG.A-hang up-PERF
'I hung up the hook.'
tampayn ta -ka -apca -r -m
NEG-1SG.A-hang up-PERF-VII.SG.O
'I didn't hang up the hook.'
 - This criterion often at odds with the phonological
 - Ex.: mamam p -na -waca-k -m -t̃ -n
Sore.VII.SG VII.SG.S-DEF-small-IRR-VII.SG-become-PRES
'The sore is getting smaller.'
Waca-k-m 'small-IRR-VII.SG' derived nominal incorporated into
into the verb and forming a
grammatical unit

clear from negation:

ta -na -waca-k -m -t̂ -nt -m
NEG-DEF-small-IRR-VII.SG-become-PRES-VII.SG.S

‘is not getting smaller’

also demonstrated by valence increasing prefixes which precede the incorporated noun

- Single word by grammatical criteria, but it is not on phonological grounds:
 - Class and number concord marker on the incorporated nominal appear as the word final allomorph and not the word medial indicate word boundary
 - Stress pattern also indicate two words: p-na-wácà-k-m-t̂-n
 - phonological: /#p-na-waca-k-m#t̂n#/
 - grammatical: /#p-na-waca-k-m-t̂-n#/

coincidence only in nouns, adjectives, not in verbs

Phonology

1. segmental properties

- A palatal may not occur stem initially or finally, except palatal lateral which can occur finally
- Voiceless aspirated allophones of stops occur in initial position and before stressed vowels; ex.: t̂kay [tH'kHáy] ‘nose’
- Stops are not orally released preceding a nasal; ex.: ir̂pm [íR'p°m] ‘coconut palm’
- /p/, /t/, /k/, /c/ must always occur stem internally with a couple of exceptions (likely to be loans)
- all CC-clusters must agree in palatality; ex.: */rc/ but /lc/
- words can begin in a vowel or any consonant other than /r/, /c/, /r̄/, /l/
- /r/ may not occur word initially or finally
- /c/, /N/ may not occur stem or word finally
- consonant-vowel-skeletal-structure: #(C)(C)V([(C)C(C)]ⁿ)V(C)(C)#
 - affixes and roots confirm to this CV-structure
 - simplest word is a vowel; ex.: i- ‘say’
 - ⁿ allows the medial syllable to iterate this syllable a number of times
 - longest root around five or six syllables, but words can be much larger

2. consonant clusters

- at phonetic level initial and final clusters are strongly constrained but they are rather freer word medially
- clusters of no more than two consonants can begin a word
- permissible combinations are any stop other than /c/ plus /r/ or /p,k/ plus /w/; ex.: pramuN ‘sleep’

- initial cluster of homorganic nasal plus stop are permitted
- palatal nasals plus stop initial clusters are prohibited by the general ban on initial palatals
- non homorganic nasal plus stop clusters are common
- fewer than 10 stems begin with a nasal plus stop cluster (great majority : mp)
- words begin with up to two consonants:
 - o #(C)(C)V
 - o if the second C is missing, the first may be any consonant except the palatals and /r/
 - o if all two C are present only the following combinations are allowed:
 - non-palatal stop + /r/
 - /p, k/ + /w/
 - nasal + homorganic stop
- final clusters more restricted:
 - o end in any C except /c/, /r/, /r/
 - o the only final C-clusters are a stop plus a homorganic nasal (always syllabic)
 - o final V(C)(C)#
- geminates are not permitted
- medial clusters:
 - o up to three C permitted
 - o clusters of two C:
 - first type: nasal + stop/nasal, but not homorganic/semivowel/ not allowed: liquid
 - second type: stop + nasal/ liquid, but not /l// semivowel/ not allowed: stop
 - 3rd type: liquid + stop (/l/ only with /c/ and not /rt/)/ nasal(/l/ only with /r/ and not /rn/)/ semivowel (only /rw/) / not allowed: liquid
 - o clusters of three consonants:
 - most of these involve a nasal + stop cluster
 - 1st type: nasal + stop + /r/ or /w/ - if /w/ - require the stop and nasal to be homorganic and peripheral (i.e. velar or labial)
 - 2nd type: liquid or stop + peripheral nasal + peripheral stop
 - the medial nasals in these two types are always syllabic
 - 3rd type: /r/ + peripheral stop + nasal or /w/

3. processes

- vowel [^] function as linking vowel – breaking up nonpermissible consonant clusters:
ex.: am- ‘eat’ + -t ‘PERF’ > am[^]t (1):
 - o applies from left to right
 - o underlying form can be vowelless
 - o may not apply at a syllable break
 - o sequences of this vowel + nasal may be realized as a syllabic nasal provided it is flanked by two stops one of which must be homorganic
- u – insertion:
 - o when adjoining syllable contains /u/ or /w/;
ex.: makuNm ‘vein’ + -l DL > maNkumul ‘veins DL’

- i – insertion :
 - o when adjoining syllable contains /i/ or /y/
 - o very restricted application between verb stem and suffixes ;
ex.: nakat^hmayk ‘I call him’ + -kiak PAST > nakt^hmaykikiak
- there are different allophonic rules for vowels: one which concerns boundaries: /u/ [μ/_ m {C/#}] (for other rules p.45)
- when /i/ comes in contact with /w/ or /y/ through morphological processes it becomes /u/ or /i/; ex.: anti- ‘hear’ + -wat HAB > antuwat ‘usually hear’
- productive rule of nasal truncation: reducing sequences of nasal to one;
ex.: pamuNk + i > [pámgi]
- Tendency for younger speakers to merge /n/ and /N/ initially
- Only major allophonic rule concerning nasals syllabifies them in final position after a homorganic stop;
ex.: yaracukNkwí [yáRv^sùk^oNgwí] ‘white PL’
- Stops are generally voiced following nasals though this optional;
ex.: kumpwí [kHúmbwí] ‘flying fox’
- /p/, /k/ are subject to allophonic rule of lenition:
 - o /p/ is likely to be voiced before a high back vowel;
ex.: irpullák [íbul^lík] ‘black ants’
 - o before /w/, /p/ is likely to be voiced and lenited to [β]
 - o lenition is more common with /k/: intervocally before an unstressed vowel becomes optionally voiced and spirantized to [f];
ex.: wak^hnt^ht [waf^hnd^ht] ‘snakes’
 - o in final syllables this lenited /k/ disappears completely with compensatory vowel lengthening;
ex.: amanak^hn [v^mv^{ná:n}] ‘1SG POSS’
- /k/: intervocally realized simply as the voiceless slit dental fricative /s/, but this varies according to age
 - o following consonants it is invariably a stop for all speakers, voiced when following a nasal
- palatalization:
 - o of a following apical dental by a preceding front vowel or semivowel
 - o preceding /i/ or /y/ may be retained or disappear
 - o no examples involving /l/
 - o ex.: tay- ‘see’ + -nak IMP > tay^hak ~ ta^hak ‘look at it’
- Liquid Strengthening:
 - o r t / _#
 - o liquid t / _nasal[-peripheral]
 - o ex.: /tkr/ t^hk^htnan ‘in the chair’
 - o liquid dissimilation: not permitted two liquids to appear in adjacent syllables separated only by a vowel if this is the case the second becomes /t/
- spreading of the autosegment R [round]:
 - o spread from one vowel to that of an adjoining syllable provided they are only separated by a peripheral consonant or cluster
 - o ex.: /awNk/ ‘egg’ + /-l/ DL > awNkul ‘eggs’ DL
 - o application is subject to lexically and grammatically specified exceptions
 - o one may speak of vowel harmony for roundness
- deletion of unstressed /u/ at morpheme boundaries in environments that will produce

certain acceptable consonant clusters;

ex.: /pu-/ 'go' + -ra REVERSE > pra 'come'

- medial semivowel formation I:
 - o applies word internally
 - o when a vowel with an associated autosegment precedes /a/ the corresponding semivowel is inserted between the vowel and the /a/
 - o ex.: ki- + -a- > kiya- verb prefix for CLASS VI PL
- medial vowel formation II:
 - o applies word internally
 - o when a morpheme ending in /a/ precedes a morpheme beginning in a vowel associated with an autosegment the corresponding semivowel is inserted
 - o ex.: naka '1SG/3SG' + -ul 'put in water' > nakawul 'put it in water'
- vowel truncation:
 - o occurs at morpheme boundaries
 - o when two vowels lacking either autosegment come together deletion of one
 - o ex.: amana- '1SG PROG' + am^hr 'eat' > amanaam^hn or amanam^hn 'I am eating'
- consonant truncation:
 - o deletion of a final stop after a homorganic nasal
 - o ex.: /impramp/ 'basket type' + O 'SG' > impram
 - o deletion of one (always the second) of two nasals in adjoining syllables at morpheme boundaries if they are followed by a stop (not obligatory)
 - o ex.: /nampunmp/ 'wing' + /-l/ DL > nampunp^hl or nampun^hmp^hl

4. *syllabification*

- if a single C occurs between two vowels the syllable boundary precedes the C (V.CV)
- in clusters of 2 C it falls between the two C unless it is a

5. *Stress*

- marked by higher pitch and somewhat lengthened vowel
- not distinctive
- primary stress to first syllable, secondary to third, if the word is longer than three syllables
- stress rules apply to the underlying form of words epenthetic vowels can't be stressed if they are in first syllable
- ex.: námarawt 'person', wúratàkay 'turtle', yáwkawpùnumprum 'yellow possum'
- surface phonetic constraint: one of the first two syllables must contain primary stress if both vowels are epenthetic then the first one carries stress;
ex.: /tkt/ 't^hk^ht 'chair'
 - o there are irregularities in pentasyllabic words of this type: when the vowel of the third syllable is also epenthetic, stress is retracted to the penultimate syllable; ex.: /kntkcki/ 'k^hnt^hk^h«c^hki 'bird (sp.)'
- problem 1: with words in which the first two vowels in the phonetic form are [u]
 - o ex.: [tupúk] 'sago pancake' [túmpun] 'clouds'
 - o difference can be accounted for by proposing the underlying forms:

- CCVC
 - t p R k (R = autosegment roundness)
 - contains an underlying vowel, which receives primary stress

- CCCC
 - t m p n
 - R
 - Simply a sequence of consonants associated with autosegments R, which is not anchored to any specific V position
 - lacks any underlying vowel, so primary stress is attracted to the first syllable

- problem 2: concerns many disyllabic or trisyllabic words with underlying vowels in the first two syllables, especially when these vowels are /a/
 - primary stress varies freely between first or second syllable
 - ex.: áwa ~ awá ‘cassowary’, yánara ~ yanára ‘bark of clove trees’
- problem 3: morphological complex forms
 - number of suffixes of nouns and corresponding adjectival/ possessive concord suffix typically occur with secondary stress
 - ex.: ‘leg’ SG: pámuN DL: pámk¹ PL: pámki
- problem 4: adjectival verbs
 - final vowel of the root always take secondary stress when followed by the irrealis tense suffix –k and a nominal concord marker regardless of the number of syllables of the stem
 - blocks the operation of the secondary stress rule
 - ex.: wál¹àk¹n ‘light’
- problem 5: verbs inflected with pronominal prefixes
 - prefixes normally unstressed
 - stress rule applies to the root
 - ex.: na -mpu -wapát¹cut
3SG.O-3PL.A-climb -RM.PAST
‘They climbed it (the tree).’

Morphology and Syntax

- Agglutinative morphology – predominantly prefixing, but also an extensive array of suffixes as well
- portmanteau morphemes indicating both class and number – two sets:
 - adjectival: suffixes – generally of the same phonological form as the final consonant or consonant cluster
 - verbal: prefixes – corresponding to the final C and sometimes to the preceding vowel of the noun stem
- inanimate phonological based classes:
 - if stem ends in C-cluster – the verbal prefix is simply the final consonant
 - if stem ends in VC sequence – verbal prefix is the metathesis of this: CV
- Order of words is generally quite irrelevant in determining meaning
- case suffix bound: a single one -¹n ~ -nan – mark locational, instrumental nominals

- ex. dependent verbs:
 mar^hmp-^hn awNkwi -mp -i ant^h- nan yampara-mp-i ama-t^hpaN-^ht
 river -OBL down.in.water-SEQ-DEP ground-OBL stand-SEQ-DEP 1SG.S –
 bathe-PERF
 ‘I went down into the river, stood on the ground and washed.’ (1)

2. Reduplication

- derives verb stems from roots
- uncommon feature
- can be:
 - full: whole stem (minus the final stop in a few cases);
 ex.: tikak > tikitak
 - copied in full without autosegment truncation
 - partial: a non-initial consonant or homorganic nasal plus stop cluster and an adjoining low vowel
 - if there is no V only the C is reduplicated
 - when involving /r/ the second /r/ becomes /t/ by the dissimilation rule
 - only the vowel /a/ reduplicated
 - autosegments associated with vowel not copied
 - ex.: api- ‘put in’ > apapi-, wul- ‘put down’ > wur^ht-, tal- ‘hold’ > tarat-
 - choice is stated in lexical entry
 - ex.: ark ‘break’ > arkark
 - couple of cases completely irregular full reduplication
 - ex.: taw- ‘sit’ > tantaw-
 - phonological rules apply to forms produced by reduplication;
 ex.: tay > tacay (palatalization)
 - reduplication to the left

3. Noun noun compounding

- split between phonological and grammatical word
- productive system employing oblique case suffix on first member
- each noun in a compound is one phonological word (stress!)
- compound as whole forms one grammatical word (inflection!)
- ex.: kálk-n ápra
 sago pudding.V.SG-OBL plate.VII.PL
 ‘plates of sago pudding’

4. Noun incorporation

- verb stem derivation from roots
- rather rare
- idiom-like structures – exceptions: incorporation of nominalized adjectives, adjectival

verbs

- exists alternative construction in which the noun is not incorporated
- ex.: patn wayk-r -mpwi pia -ka -na -yaNkuraN -takat-n
betelnut.V.SG buy -NFN-talk talk.O-1SG.A-DEF-thoughts.VI.SG-feel-PRES
'I am thinking about buying betelnut.'

5. Adverbial incorporation

- two types of adverbs:
 - o can only appear incorporated;
 - o ex.: na -mpu -pay -kulanaN-tay-⁻cut
V.SG.O-3PL.A-first-walk -see-RM.PAST
'They walked around and looked at it first.'
 - o Either incorporated or independent;
ex.: na-n -mampi-ira -wampuNkra-ntut
3SG.O-3SG.A-again -ALL-angry -RM.PAST
'He was angry with her again.'

6. locational postpositions

- contrast with free locationals in not always being independent words
- may also be used as free locationals
- derived from nouns (marked with OBL), some still nouns
- instead might be used verb prefixes
- four other postpositions = grammatical postpositions – preceding noun, never marked with OBL function like case markers
- ex.: panmal naykum kantk na -na -wa-n
man.I.SG woman.II.PL with 3SG-DEF-go-PRES
'The man is going with the women.'